

Fuzzy-Logic Based Model for VANET Performance Metrics Analysis

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Abstract

Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks (VANETs) allow spontaneous communication between vehicle-to-vehicle and Road-Side Units (RSU) using wireless interfaces and road-side infrastructure to form an Intelligent Transportation System (ITS). VANET, prime objective is to provide information about accidents or unwanted situations and traffic conditions to the drivers. As VANETs are dynamic in nature, the vehicle nodes to discover the best possible route to broadcast an emergency message is a challenge. To study different highway and urban road scenarios, there is a need to simulate and evaluate the network performance analysis of routing protocols beforehand since the real-time implementation is rather challenging or expensive. This paper focuses on the VANET routing protocols evaluation, to find an appropriate protocol that provides suitable Quality of Service (QoS) to end users in both safety and non-safety conditions. To simplify the QoS evaluation problem, the Hierarchical Fuzzy Inference System (HFIS) model has been designed and simulated in MATLAB R2018b which analyzes the network performance metrics of VANET routing protocols. From the simulations, it is observed that the OLSR routing protocol for both safety and non-safety applications, outperforms other routing protocols as its global QoS reaches approximately 84% efficiency.

Index Terms: Fuzzy Logic, Intelligent Transportation System, Quality of Service, Routing Protocols, Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to a study conducted by the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 1.19 million people die every year due to traffic accidents [1], and 1 million rupees are being wasted daily because of traffic jams [2]. As the quality of life depends to a particular degree on the road transportation system in developing societies, the adoption of Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks (VANETs) will be the best-suited option to achieve a safe and comfortable transportation system. Every participating vehicle represents a mobile node that enables the network at about every 300 meters to 1 km, to establish a communicating network. The primary aim of VANET is to disseminate real-time traffic information and safety messages to vehicles. This technology can enhance traffic conditions and reduce traffic congestion by providing valuable data to drivers and passengers, such as road-side alerts, in-place traffic views, and collision warnings.

To provide transportation comfort the Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) has used Vehicle-To-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-To-Infrastructure (V2I), where vehicles communicate with a Road-Side Unit (RSU) using Wireless Access in Vehicular Environment (WAVE) architecture and a Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) technology [3], and [4].

A. Urban Deployment for Vehicular Adhoc Network

In urban cities, the streets and nearby areas have complex road infrastructure, therefore, the vehicle driver has

numerous communication and information transmission alternatives between cars. Furthermore, the limited speed of vehicles in rural areas is limited to less than 20 km/h, raising the delay time for transmitting messages. Unfortunately, in cities, there are numerous intersections and buildings that hinder transmission and cause signal attenuation and data loss. Hence, to deal with such problems, a multi-hop broadcast protocol can be used. Figure I depicts the Urban Environment and deployment of VANET architecture.

B. Applications of Vehicular Ad-hoc Network (VANET)

The applications of VANETs may be classified according to the passenger's requirements and service provision. At the same time, the user necessities can be comfort applications like weather forecasts, traffic detection with alternative route options, toll payments, near fuel stations, internet access, or music downloads. Services of utmost priority are safety applications like accident detection, car brake failure, intersection collision warning, and hazardous location warning. The implementation of VANET applications is demonstrated in figure II.

Under various conditions, the consumer's requirements are different while using VANET services. Thus, their view of the system's performance is also different. The research objective is to do an analysis of the network performance metrics of VANETs routing protocol and design a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) model to evaluate QoS parameters for different service provisions related to VANET applications.

Figure I: VANET Urban Deployment

Figure II: VANET Applications [4]

This paper covered the following sections: Section II, the VANET routing protocols, Section III related work, Section IV Performance metrics parameters. Section V, simulation results. Section VI the Hierarchical Fuzzy Inference System (HFIS) Model Implementation. Section VII, conclusion and future work.

II. VANET ROUTING PROTOCOLS

The main features of VANET are the high mobility of vehicles, autonomous connectivity and communication of nodes, a random-sized network, the lifetime of links, and road conditions. Due to the high flexibility of nodes, message delivery in VANETs is a challenge. As cars travel fast and randomly, establishing the best message-routing path to destination vehicles is complex. As a result, routing algorithms must be well-organized and adjust to the features and applications of vehicular networks. Emphasis must be given to designing routing protocols that can accommodate the VANET's heterogeneity. The topology-based routing protocol is classified as follows:

A. Proactive Routing

Also called a table-driven protocol. It keeps all node route information in the network routing table. It broadcasts a message to update the routing tables regularly, which increases overhead, but the route is always accessible.

- Destination Sequence Distance Vector (DSDV)

The Destination Sequence Distance Vector (DSDV) uses a distance vector shortest path routing algorithm. There are two sorts of routing table updates: "full dump" and "incremental." In order to reduce the amount of traffic generated, incremental packets only carry updated information and reduce bandwidth utilization. As incremental packet delivery is so frequent, it still increases network overhead, making it incompatible with a widespread VANET network [5].

- Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR)

It tracks the routing data by providing information about the link state. Every node transmits updates to selected nodes after each topology change. Each node in the network will thus only be updated once. Topology control messages are used to transmit their neighbor information over the Multi-Point Relay (MPR) [6].

B. Reactive Routing

Another name for it is the "On-Demand Routing Protocol". The route is constructed as needed by the flooding process and is updated regularly. It reduces overhead and is more appropriate for frequent topology changes and large mobility networks.

- Ad-hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV)

It sends the message when it is required by the source node vehicle to broadcast the alert. Upon receiving a request from the destination node, the source node broadcasts a message instantly. When a route is not available, ADOV floods the Route request packet in the network to the desired destination. The source node notifies its neighbor with a Route Request (RREQ) message when it desires a route to go to the destination. The node neighbor

broadcasts the RREQ repeatedly until the RREQ returns the request [7]. If any of its neighbors' routes reach the target, it acknowledges the route with reply messages i.e., Route Reply (RREP).

- Dynamic Source Routing (DSR)

It is a dynamic, self-configured, and self-arranged protocol. This protocol contains two activities, "Route Discovery" and "Route Maintenance". Without a centralized administrator or infrastructure, it manages the VANET network. The primary goal of the Dynamic Source Routing (DSR) protocol is to reduce network overhead by inventing a spontaneous and self-configuration network [8] that relies on the minimum hop count parameter to provide the path without considering any other factors such as energy consumption and node energy level, which significantly affect the routing algorithm performance.

III. RELATED WORK

In a routing study in VANETs, the authors in [9] used the method for forwarder selection to classify routing protocols as broadcast, position, geo-cast, and cluster-based routing protocols. Similarly, in [10] authors proposed a topology-based routing protocol, and comparison research was conducted in VANETs of different routing protocols. In [11], the author proposed an ANT Colony Optimization method for the QoS-OLSR protocol and determined End-To-End (E2E) Delay, latency, PDR, and overhead QoS factors. A broadcast protocol for VANETs based on a lightweight retransmission mechanism was proposed by the authors in [12]. The overhead, delay, jitter, and delivery rate of DSR, AODV, and DSDV were investigated by the authors of [13] to identify the protocol that offers the best quality of service (QoS) and flexibility in VANET scenarios. The authors in [14] utilized the fuzzy system to determine the QoS of DSR, AODV, and DSDV, by increasing the node numbers in the network and evaluated that in terms of data transmission and latency, AODV Protocol performs better than the DSDV and DSR protocols.

Authors in [15] designed a generic fuzzy system model for determining the E2E delay and PDR for QoS-OLSR, UMB, and V-TRADE VANET protocols. In [16], utilize NS-3 to assess performance metrics: PLR, OH & throughput for OLSR AODV, & DSDV routing protocol. The authors of [17] used a Device-To-Device (D2D) architecture to examine several QoS metrics in vehicular communications, including PDR, throughput, BER, latency, and PLR. In [18], QoS measurements of AODV, DSR, and DSDV protocol are based on MANET by varying network capacity and dimension. It was found that, for the network dimension scenario, DSDV gives improved performance in terms of Throughput, PDR, and PLR. While, for the network capacity the DSR performance was improved in terms of Throughput, PDR, and PLR.

Authors in [19] determined the performance of vehicle routing protocols using NS-3. Performance metrics include Good put and PDR. AODV seems to be an excellent low-density vehicle routing system, while OLSR overcomes the other high-density methods. The authors of [20]

examined the QoS performance metrics of topology and geographic routing protocols. In [21], authors examined AODV, OLSR, and DSDV routing protocols with the VANET scenario utilizing the PDR, Good put, Routing Overhead, and E2E Delay assessed simulators using NS-3 and Bonn Motion and concluded that OLSR was the best protocol.

IV. PERFORMANCE METRICS PARAMETERS

A. Packet Delivery Ratio

It is the ratio between the number of Packets sent (P_s) and Packets received (P_r) from a target node to the source. This option provides the loss rate for a protocol, specifying the accuracy of routing protocols. Various factors such as packet and cluster size, spreading radius, node speed, and mobility model may affect the PDR parameter.

$$PDR = \frac{\sum Pr}{\sum Ps} \quad (1)$$

B. Average End-to-End Delay

Determines how long it usually takes for a data packet to travel from its source to its destination node. Network performance can be enhanced by lowering the delay value. Delays in processing, queuing, propagation, and transmission all contribute to network delays. The treatment becomes less effective as delays increase.

$$D = \frac{\sum Pr(at-st)}{\sum NC} \quad (2)$$

C. Throughput

It is the proportion of the total amount of packets received, plus the size of each packet, to the overall simulation time.

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{\text{Total No: of Received Packets} * \text{Packet Size}}{\text{Total Simulation Time}} \quad (3)$$

D. Overhead

It is the proportion between routing packets to be delivered for communication ($P_{delivered}$) and the amount of communication routing packets (P_{total}) needed.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this study, four routing protocols OLSR, DSDV, AODV, and DSR are chosen. The simulation is performed in two service scenarios: Scenario-1 for Safety and Scenario-2 for non-safety. Simulations are carried out on a two-lane road in the 2 km² urban area with node velocity set to 20 Km/h. S1 comprises 40 nodes, and S2 comprises 80 nodes, respectively. The simulation duration is 20s. The network parameters are shown in table I.

The simulation is performed under the operating system. Ubuntu 20.04, comprising 8 GB of RAM with an Intel Core i5 3.2 GHz processor by using SUMO 1.7 as a mobility generator and NS-2.35 as a network simulator.

The objective of the simulation is to analyze performance metrics and factors: Packet Delivery Ratio, Overhead, Throughput, and End-to-End Delay. The mobility traces collected by SUMO are exported into Network Simulator (NS-2.35) using the trace exporter python file. After the execution of the network file, The Network Animator

(NAM) simulation demonstrates the graphic representation of network nodes for broadcasting messages in the VANET system as shown in figure III.

Table I: Simulation Parameters

Parameters	Values
Area	2 km ²
Topology	Two Lanes Road
Number of Nodes	For Scenario-1= 40, For Scenario-2= 80
Node Velocity	20 km/h
Mobility Simulator	SUMO
Network Simulator	NS-2.35
MAC Type/ Phy type	02.11Maci802.11p
Antenna	Omnidirectional
Propagation Model	Two Ray Ground
Mobility Model	Random Way Point
Interface Queue Type	Droptail, Priority queue
Routing Protocols	AODV, OLSR, DSDV, DSR

Figure III: VANET Broadcasting

A. Network Performance Metrics

- Packet Delivery Ratio at Node Density 40

As shown in figure IV, we can observe that AODV achieved a maximum of 80% PDR at an initial 20-node density. However, the highest PDR of 98% was attained at a node density of 40 by the OLSR protocol compared to other routing protocols.

Figure IV: PDR (S1)

- Delay at Node Density 40

Figure V shows that at a node density of 20, the minimum delay of 900ms is achieved by the OLSR Protocol. However, at a node density of 40, DSDV achieved a minimum delay of approximately 2000ms.

Figure V: Delay (S1)

- Overhead at Node Density 40

Figure VI shows that overall AODV protocol performs better than other protocols. OLSR and DSR overhead increased with node density.

Figure VI: Overhead (S1)

- Packet Delivery Ratio at Node Density 80

As the node density is increased, the PDR varies. As shown in figure VII, the AODV protocol outperforms OLSR with 98% PDR compared to other routing protocols.

Figure VII: PDR (S2)

- Delay at Node Density 80

As shown in figure VIII, as the node density increases AODV protocol delay increases. In contrast, OLSR always has the lowest delay.

Figure VIII: Delay (S2)

- Throughput at Node Density 80

Figure IX illustrates the AODV throughput ratio surpasses all other routing protocols. In comparison, OLSR remains to be at the steady value of 250 Kbps throughput.

Figure IX: Throughput (S2)

- Overhead at Node Density 80

In figure X, we notice that DSR and DSDV give the highest overhead ratio. In comparison, AODV remains slightly lower than the OLSR overhead ratio. We can observe that the OLSR protocol provides a better result than other protocols.

Figure X: Overhead (S2)

These fundamental outcomes, whether for the first or second scenario, are so contradictory. As a result, it cannot

be able to determine which scheme among those is considered the most effective and hence capable of providing VANET, with the maximum level of user satisfaction. So, there should be a method through which the QoS can be evaluated for different applications. Many scientific problems have been effectively solved by utilizing fuzzy systems in recent years. A Hierarchical Fuzzy Inference System (HFIS) is proposed for VANET performance metrics analysis.

VI. HIERARCHICAL FUZZY INFERENCE SYSTEM MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

A. Hierarchical Fuzzy Inference System

Two FS layers are present in the core system, as seen in figure XI.

- Layer_1 FS

It uses the QoS factor using network simulator outputs. ‘Up_QoS’ and ‘Down_QoS’ are the two inference systems that make up the Level_1 FS. The Up_QoS parameters have a linear proportionality relation with the system quality of service such as PDR and Throughput. These factors represent the inputs to the Up_QoS. The second category QoS factors, are inversely related such as Delay and Overhead, and represented as the Down_QoS.

Figure XI: HFIS Model

- Layer_2 FS

It takes the Layer_1 FS outputs as input along with the network designer's settings (weightage and priority) and

produces the QoS values. Those values are finally blended with the weights given to get the universal QoS.

In this study, the proposed weightage allocated here are; 0.7 weight to QoS Scenario-1 and 0.3 priority to QoS Scenario-2, respectively. The fuzzy rules are applied to simulation results taken from the network simulator for AODV, DSDV, DSR, and OLSR routing the final global QoS can be calculated as mentioned in eq. (4) [22].

$$QoS = 0.7 * QoS1 + 0.3 * QoS2 \quad (4)$$

B. Fuzzy Inference Model

MATLAB R2018b is used to determine the performance metrics of VANET routing protocols. The input range values and their corresponding membership functions and rules base are all defined based on the network simulation results obtained from NS-2.35. From the Y-Axis of performance metrics, the results graph of the maximum range for both scenarios is obtained. Table II and table III indicate the lowest and highest input bounds for Scenario-1 and Scenario-2 respectively.

Table II: FUZZY Rule Base Values (S1)

Variable	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Delay	0	6
PDR	0	100
Throughput	0	200
Overhead	0	60

Table III: FUZZY Rule Base Values (S2)

Variable	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Delay	0	6
PDR	0	100
Overhead	0	80

C. Fuzzy Model Simulation Results

By using a Fuzzy-based model, for QoS evaluation, this study determines the exact value for each protocol as described in table IV and reaches the conclusion that OLSR reaches the best QoS of 0.849, although AODV has improved QoS for Scenario-2 of 0.858 but the global QoS reduces to 0.783. Thus, by using these outcomes it can be clearly observed that for both safety and non-safety scenarios OLSR will be the best-suited routing protocol for the implementation of VANET in urban city scenarios.

Table IV: Fuzzy-based Model Performance Metrics

Protocol	Up_QoS1	Down_QoS1	QoS1	Up_QoS2	Down_QoS2	QoS2	Global QoS
AODV	0.254	0.65	0.75	0.858	0.82	0.862	0.783
OLSR	0.734	0.799	0.846	0.697	0.755	0.807	0.849
DSDV	0.558	0.646	0.643	0.593	0.755	0.768	0.75
DSR	0.471	0.682	0.569	0.507	0.668	0.666	0.61

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The VANET provides both safety and non-safety applications. The prime requirement for critical message delivery is to have a minimum delay and no overhead issues and a high-quality data delivery and throughput ratio. Which requires routing protocols to transmit data to the destination vehicle to achieve the best QoS to end-users. In order to achieve the global QoS, a Fuzzy

Inference System model has been designed and simulated based on VANET applications for safety and non-safety scenarios. This model minimizes the complexity and attempts to address the QoS approximation issue-specific in a VANET. Hence, by using a Fuzzy-logic-based model the results show that for both safety and non-safety scenarios OLSR protocol gives optimum QoS by having 84% efficiency as compared to AODV, DSDV, and DSR protocols that reaches to 78%, 75%, and 61% respectively.

In future work, different VANET broadcasting protocols can be investigated and simulated through simulators like OMNET++ and NS-3. Through machine learning techniques, the broadcasting protocols can be optimized. The proposed method can help other researchers implement optimization techniques on VANET routing protocols to improve the QoS in complex network areas. The security and privacy of end users' data is a challenge in VANET broadcasting scenarios; the researchers need to work in this direction.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

All the authors mentioned above in the paper titled "Fault Detection and Fault Diagnosis in Power System Using AI" declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this research work.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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